

PREVALENCE AND SEVERITY OF DEPRESSION AMONG OPIOID USERS AT A PUBLIC SECTOR TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL, KARACHI

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Abstract

Objective: To assess the prevalence and severity of depression among opioid users at a public sector tertiary care hospital in Karachi.

Study Design: Descriptive, cross-sectional study.

Setting and Duration: Conducted at the Department of Psychiatry and Behavioral Sciences, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre, Karachi, from April 20, 2021, to October 19, 2021.

Methods: A total of 250 patients aged 18–60 years, predominantly diagnosed with opioid use disorder and presenting with depressive symptoms, were recruited from the outpatient department. Exclusion criteria included pre-existing psychiatric disorders, chronic medical illnesses, or predominant use of non-opioid substances. Sociodemographic and opioid-use data were collected using a semi-structured proforma. Depression was assessed using the Urdu version of the Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9), with scores ≥ 10 considered indicative of depression.

Results: The mean age was 36.64 ± 7.38 years, with 84% aged 18–40 years. Most participants were male (83.6%) with a male-to-female ratio of 5:1. Depression was observed in 88 patients (35.2%): 26 (10.4%) mild, 29 (11.6%) moderate, and 33 (13.2%) severe. Depression was significantly associated with marital status ($p=0.0007$), ethnicity ($p=0.0001$), education ($p=0.0001$), income ($p=0.0001$), occupation ($p=0.0001$), family type ($p=0.019$), and residence ($p=0.0005$).

Conclusion: Depression is highly prevalent among opioid users, with higher risk among those with extreme ages, lower education, unemployment, and poor socioeconomic status. Screening and appropriate mental health interventions are recommended to reduce morbidity and improve quality of life in this population.

INTRODUCTION

Depression is characterized by depressed mood, loss of interest and enjoyment, and reduced energy leading to increase fatigability and diminished

activity [1]. Opioids, including natural, synthetic, and endogenous compounds, act on central and peripheral opioid receptors to produce analgesic and

psychoactive effects [2]. These receptors are mu, kappa, and delta—mediate pain relief, sedation, euphoria, respiratory depression, and dependence [2]. The prevalence of depression among opioid users is high and ranges between 20% and 45% [2].

According to the UN Drug Control Program, around 15.6 million people globally use opioids, with 11 million using heroin [3-4]. In Pakistan, 0.8 million of the 1 million opioid users consume heroin, placing the country among the most affected by substance use [3-4]. It has been shown through different studies that opioid users show depressive symptoms more frequently [5].

The duration of opioid use also plays a significant role in the development of depression. Prolonged opioid use predisposes patients to depressive symptoms, and when a patient reports such symptoms, physicians should consider opioid analgesic use as a potential contributing factor [6]. Opioid use has been associated with increased criminal behavior, psychiatric comorbidities, and injection-related complications such as abscesses and infections [7]. Depressed patients are more prone to overusing opioids [8]. Very small number of physicians screen their patients for depression before prescribing opioids in our country [9].

Physicians prescribing opioids should routinely screen patients for prior opioid use and history of depression, as opioids can worsen depression. Alternatives to opioids may be considered to avoid these risks. Limited data on opioid-related depression in our population highlights the need for this study to promote rational opioid use and reduce the disease burden.

Methods

A descriptive cross-sectional design was employed. A sample size of 250 was calculated using the WHO calculator, assuming a 20% prevalence of depression, 95% confidence level, and 5% margin of error. Participants were recruited via non-probability consecutive sampling.

Inclusion criteria:

- Age 18–60 years, both genders
- Diagnosed predominantly with opioid use disorder
- Presenting with depressive symptoms

Exclusion criteria:

- Severe withdrawal preventing questionnaire completion
- Pre-existing depressive or other psychiatric disorders
- Chronic medical illnesses (TB, asthma, malignancies, hypertension, diabetes)
- Predominant use of substances other than opioids
- Inability to provide informed consent

Data collection followed ethical approval from the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan and the IRB of Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre. Depression was assessed via PHQ-9 Urdu version; scores ≥ 10 were considered positive.

Quantitative variables (age, income, opioid use frequency, number of dependents, PHQ-9 scores) were expressed as mean \pm SD. Categorical variables (gender, marital status, ethnicity, depression presence) were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Associations were analyzed using the Chi-square test with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results

The Table-I showing the result that study comprised 250 participants with a mean age of 36.64 ± 7.38 years. Most (84%) were 18–40 years old, 209 (83.6%) were male, and 41 (16.4%) were female. Marital status included 52.4% unmarried and 42% married. Major ethnicities were Sindhi (26.4%) and Balochi (24.4%). Educational attainment varied from no formal education (20%) to bachelor's degree (9.2%). Monthly income ranged from PKR 14,000–20,000 (58.8%) to 20,000–100,000 (41.2%).

Table -I

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Total participants	-	250	100
Age (years)	Mean ± SD	36.64 ± 7.38	-
	18-40	210	84
	>40	40	16
Gender	Male	209	83.6
	Female	41	16.4
Marital Status	Unmarried	131	52.4
	Married	105	42
	Other	14	5.6
Ethnicity	Sindhi	66	26.4
	Balochi	61	24.4
	Others	123	49.2
Education	No formal education	50	20
	Primary/Secondary	175	70.8
	Bachelor's degree	23	9.2
Monthly Income (PKR)	14,000-20,000	147	58.8
	20,000-100,000	103	41.2

Table II is showing that the Heroin was the predominant opioid (61.2%), followed by opium (15.2%) and nalbuphine (14.4%). Participants lived mainly in joint families (53.2%) and urban areas (60.4%). Occupations included businessmen (33.2%), unemployed (18.4%), and skilled professionals (15.6%).

Table -II

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Opioid Type	Heroin	153	61.2
	Opium	38	15.2
	Nalbuphine	36	14.4
	Other	23	9.2
Family Type	Joint	133	53.2
	Nuclear	117	46.8
Residence	Urban	151	60.4
	Rural	99	39.6
Occupation	Businessmen	83	33.2
	Unemployed	46	18.4
	Skilled Professionals	39	15.6
	Others	82	32.8

Table -III is showing that the Depression was identified in 88 patients (35.2%), with 26 (10.4%) mild, 29 (11.6%) moderate, and 33 (13.2%) severe. Significant associations were observed for marital

status, ethnicity, education, income, occupation, family type, and residence. No significant association was found with age, gender, opioid type, or number of dependents.

Table -III

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Depression	Present	88	35.2
	Mild	26	10.4
	Moderate	29	11.6
	Severe	33	13.2

Discussion

Copeland et al. reported wide variation in the prevalence of depression among older adults across nine European populations, consistently noting higher rates in females, with no uniform trend across age groups. Meta-analytic evidence further supports an overall prevalence of 12.3%, with 14.1% in females and 8.6% in males[10]. Structural neuroimaging research has also demonstrated that major depressive disorder is associated with enlarged lateral ventricles and cerebrospinal fluid spaces, along with reduced volumes in the basal ganglia, thalamus, hippocampus, frontal lobe, orbitofrontal cortex, and gyrus rectus. Notably, hippocampal volume tends to be lower during active depressive episodes compared with periods of remission [11].

Although depression is influenced by multiple genetic factors, genes regulating serotonin pathways have remained central to research interest, largely because many antidepressant medications exert their therapeutic effects through serotonergic mechanisms [12]. In line with this, the American Psychiatric Association’s 2011 guidelines recommend selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) as first-line agents for children, adolescents, and individuals with late-onset depression owing to their favorable dosing profile and low risk of toxicity in overdose [13].

Mood and anxiety disorders frequently co-occur among opioid users, a relationship that may reflect neurobiological changes induced by opioids, self-medication of distressing symptoms, or shared vulnerability factors [14]. In the current study, depressive symptoms were identified in 35.2% of opioid users, including 10.4% with mild, 11.6% with moderate, and 13.2% with severe depression.

Comparable findings have been observed elsewhere; in a sample of 100 opioid users, one study reported 21% mild, 48% moderate, and 13% severe depressive symptoms [15].

The demographic pattern in our sample aligns with earlier reports. The mean age was 36.64 ± 7.38 years, with the majority falling between 18 and 40 years. Similar age distributions have been documented by Prasant et al [16]., who found that 72% of individuals with opioid dependence syndrome (ODS) were under 30 years of age. Collectively, these findings reinforce that opioid dependence disproportionately affects younger age groups, likely influenced by factors such as peer dynamics, sensation seeking, limited coping strategies, cultural changes, and socioeconomic stressors.

In terms of gender, 83.6% of the participants in our study were male, producing a male-to-female ratio of 5:1. This is consistent with several previous studies reporting higher opioid use and dependence among males. [17-18], Fischer et al. further highlighted that non-medical opioid consumption occurs across diverse demographic and socioeconomic backgrounds, potentially driven by greater accessibility, affordability, and purchasing power among men [19-20].

Educational patterns in the present study also mirror existing literature, with 55% of participants educated up to the secondary level. Ahmadi et al. similarly found that most opioid users had only elementary or high school education [18-21]. Marital status trends were also comparable: 52% of our sample were unmarried, a distribution consistent with findings from Datta et al., where the majority of opioid users were single[17].

Urban residence was reported by 60% of participants, closely reflecting observations by Mattoo et al., who found that 80% of opioid-dependent individuals originated from urban settings [22]. Finally, heroin emerged as the most commonly used opioid in our study (61.2%), corroborating United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime estimates that out of approximately one million opioid users in Pakistan, about 0.8 million are heroin users[4].

Overall, the demographic, clinical, and substance-use profiles observed in this study are in close agreement with regional and international evidence, underscoring the persistent public health burden of opioid dependence and its strong association with depressive symptoms.

Conclusion

Depression is highly prevalent among opioid users, particularly in individuals with extreme age groups, low education, unemployment, and poor socioeconomic status. Routine mental health screening, counseling, and psychotherapy should be incorporated into substance use management to reduce morbidity and improve quality of life.

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